

**THE "GOLDEN PATH". MASS COMMUNICATION EDUCATION AND
JOURNALISM IN UZBEKISTAN AND IN THE UNITED STATES.**

Shakhnoza Uzakova Beknazarovna

An assistant teacher at Roman-German Philology Faculty,
Linguistics department at Karshi State University, Kashkadarya, Uzbekistan
e-mail (shakhnozauzakova@gmail.com)

Contact Number: (+998973102022)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7156141>

Annotatsiya. Jurnalistika atamasi butun dunyoda paydo bo'lganidan beri ommaviy kommunikatsiya ta'limi va jurnalistika doimo butun dunyo bo'ylab qizg'in muhokama qilinadigan masalalardan biri bo'lib kelgan. Ba'zilar jurnalistika ta'limi akademik sohaning bir bo'lagi bo'lishi kerak deb hisoblasa, boshqalari ommaviy kommunikatsiya ta'limi asosan kasbiy yoki kasbiy mahoratga asoslanadi, deb o'ylaydi. Bu tezis asosan AQSh va O'zbekiston talabalari misolida jurnalistika ta'limini o'rganishning ahamiyatiga qaratilgan.

Аннотация. Образование в области массовых коммуникаций и журналистика всегда были одним из самых горячо обсуждаемых вопросов во всем мире с тех пор, как сам термин журналистика появился во всем мире. В то время как некоторые считают, что журналистское образование должно быть частью академической области, другие считают, что образование в области массовых коммуникаций в основном основано на профессиональных или профессиональных навыках, которые необходимо приобрести. Этот тезис в основном фокусируется на важности изучения журналистского образования на выборках студентов США и Узбекистана

Annotation. Mass communication education and journalism have always been one of the hot debated issues around the globe since the term of journalism itself appeared worldwide. While some believe that journalism education should be one part of academic field, others seem that mass communication education is mostly based on vocational or professional skill that one has to acquire. This thesis mainly focuses on the importance of learning journalism education in the samples of the USA and Uzbekistan students.

Kalit so'zlar: jurnalistika ta'limi, ommaviy axborot vositalari, ommaviy ishlab chiqarish, aloqa, professional jurnalistlar, AQSh, hikoya

Ключевые слова: журналистское образование, массовое производство, коммуникация, профессиональные журналисты, США, нарратив.

Key words: journalism education, mass media, mass production, communication, professional journalists, the USA, narrative

Introduction. During the first decades of the 21st century, not only the USA but other countries also underwent new challenges in teaching journalism and mass communication in college and universities. There were three inevitable challenges occurred that should be looked through in this article. First and foremost, the programs aimed to display journalism and mass communication found it difficult to adapt and maintain their path to the rapid media technologies that have been developing since 1980s. Although we cannot deny that numerous numbers of universities worldwide are offering online courses to study journalism courses, majority of these university authorities cannot give details about the main differences between the materials in print and different courses on broadcast media at all.

The next, majority of graduate students of journalism and mass communication programs are suffering from the lack of vacancies and offered services in traditionally accepted broadcasts, print, advertising but are excessively moving into other types of communicational aspects, namely public affairs or governmental organizations. As a result, current available journalism education programs in both the United States and in Uzbekistan mainly cover general communication skills rather than specifically to news media itself.

Lastly, developing globalization and multicultural societies around the globe are becoming one of the important challenges. In other words, in many journalism institutions and mass communication programs students are still being taught according to national perspective (Cottle, 2000). The main problem is here, the world requires more intelligent and knowledgeable journalists who are aware of other cultures and ethnicities. Moreover, they have to know about cross cultures and ethnics (Deuze, 2001). However, the current developing economic globalization, multiculturalism as well as system of mass media require the journalists with enhanced knowledge about culture varieties, their ethnicities, a wide variety of intercultural communications in a workplace where occurs different cultural societies (Deuze, 2001).

Fortunately, it is undoubtedly fact that the US media courses and programs have already started to cover and respond to the abovementioned points and challenges.

As for mass media development in Uzbekistan, it has been offering a powerful media that gives a great opportunity for official narratives to make more critical coverage in order to create more independent and pluralistic atmosphere. In the past few decades professional journalists were in high demand as there were not any suitable and meaningful trainings for journalists. There were scarce

places to gain journalism education for journalists and there were hardly ever trainings for them. Therefore, more professional and energetic journalists had to abandon the country. Yet, in the past decade, there have been opened some university faculties providing journalism education for the youth in order to fill the place of those who left to other countries. Moreover, it is obvious fact that because of the abundance of internet connection, we can witness a wide variety of channels that represent various programs that are broadcasted by journalists. However, it still remains as a huge problem to find talented and professional journalists (Nikita Makarenko, 2020).

(The statistical picture is derived from <https://voicesoncentralasia.org/on-the-uzbek-media-development-an-interview-with-nikita-makarenko/> that is surveyed by “Public opinion” Institute)

According to the table, we can see that TV is the most common type of information source among all ages of people.

Conclusion. Journalism education and mass media in Uzbekistan and in the United States are facing a number of difficulties that should be taken into consideration. Likewise, theoretical or practical effectiveness is still remaining as a hot issue. For this, in the past decades there has been opening journalism faculties in some institutions and have been contributing by training professional journalists. Still, some challenges occur in teaching mass communication that are mentioned above. Thus, in the upcoming years it is

predictable that news coming through the internet will be widespread among all nations.

References:

1. Deuze, M. (2001). Journalism education and multiculturalism: Enhancing the curriculum. *Asia Pacific Media Educator*, 10, 127-147
2. Deuze, M. (2001) educating “new” journalists: Challenges to the curriculum. *Journalism and Mass Communication Educator*, 56.
3. Johnstone, J, Slawski, E., (1976). *The news people: A sociological portrait of American journalists and their work.*
4. <https://voicesoncentralasia.org/on-the-uzbek-media-development-an-interview-with-nikita-makarenko/>

